

THE ROLE OF PRACTICAL EXERCISES IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS

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Annotation. The author of the article emphasizes that an important factor ensuring the effectiveness of this process is the formation of a new approach to the organization of complex practical activities - training. Conducting classes using non-traditional forms, methods, technologies and means gives its positive results and ensures their effectiveness.

Key words: training, professional schools, student activity, skills formation.

The problem of training qualified personnel occupies a special place in the system of socio-economic reforms carried out in our republic, a special place is occupied by the processes of modernization of the national economy. In accordance with the requirements of the labor market, a competitive system of personnel training has been formed and is being developed. In matters of reforming the domestic education system, issues of developing integration between types of education are becoming increasingly important. Integration is a key factor in the development of skilled professionals.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 6, 2019 No. PF-5812 “On additional measures to further improve the system of vocational education” serves as a programmatic action to further develop unity and continuity between general secondary, secondary specialized and higher education system. According to the decree, “primary, secondary and secondary specialized vocational schools have been granted the right to train personnel in educational programs of a lower level in addition to the main educational programs according

to the International Classification. The system will create a network of vocational educational institutions, consisting of vocational schools, colleges and technical institutes [1], where programs of primary, secondary and secondary specialized vocational education are introduced, respectively. According to the decree, vocational schools established from the 2020-2021 academic year will be formed at the expense of graduates of the 9th grade on the basis of integrated science programs, and they will be provided with vocational education in the form of full-time education for 2 years.

Based on the content of pedagogical activity aimed at the effective organization of vocational schools and the nature of observations, it should be noted that an important factor ensuring the effectiveness of this process is the formation of a new approach to the organization of complex practical activities - training. Conducting classes using non-traditional forms, methods, technologies and means gives its positive results and ensures their effectiveness.

At the same time: determination of didactic conditions that make it possible to increase the effectiveness of training; development of content and a consistent system of topics for organized professionally oriented education; creation of educational and methodical literature of a new generation; to involve in this process engineer-educators with special pedagogical knowledge, and to achieve a systematic increase in their pedagogical and professional knowledge; formation of a technological approach to the organization of training in them; in this process, it is necessary to determine ways to ensure the activity of students, to form the skills of independent reading and assimilation of knowledge related to professional fields [2].

This can be determined by such criteria as increasing the efficiency of vocational schools, creating their effective system, providing them with modern technical means, developing students' independence and activity, and developing a high level of professional knowledge and skills among students.

To increase the effectiveness of training in vocational schools, to ensure its

overall design, to determine the goals and objectives of the topics expressed within the framework of a particular course aimed at its organization, to carefully determine the tasks that need to be completed to achieve In it, for the development of the content of educational topics, are of great importance organizational form, method, technology and choice of means, determination of forms, methods and methods of general control of professional activity.

The importance of organizing classes, increasing their effectiveness, preparing students for vocational training for independent work in accordance with their own characteristics, striving to find their place in the micro-society, determining their life goal, improving their moral behavior, strict definition of the direction of professional activity will be [3].

The role of the school team in the effective organization of classes is important. If this team accepts the presence of students in group training as a responsibility for them, then they will create favorable conditions for the success of this process. This, in turn, serves to improve the activities of vocational schools. Indeed, in it, teacher-engineers provide direct assistance to students in comprehending the secrets of the profession. As a result, efficiency is increased.

Therefore, it is advisable to carry out preparatory work in advance at the place of internship. Successful internship depends, first of all, on the preparation of students for it, and it is advisable to conduct it in the following order: obtaining advice from a specialist teacher (concepts that should be given the main attention when studying a new subject, equipment, using the necessary methods, achieving a learning unit etc.), determine the content of the topics studied in practical classes and study it in depth, familiarize yourself with the scientific and methodological literature on the topic, determine the relationship of the topic being studied with other subjects and previous topics, determine the structure and purpose of teaching methods, based on this draw up a plan, on the basis of this plan, conduct classes, develop a methodology and prepare the necessary teaching aids, monitor and evaluate students' knowledge, determine the size and form of homework, draw up a

summary plan for training.

It should be noted that the conditions created to achieve the effectiveness of practical exercises are of great importance. To do this, it is necessary to create the following conditions: organization and conduct of training based on a specific goal; taking into account the internal needs, desires of students, as well as physical and psychological characteristics; organization of training using various forms, methods, technologies and means; regularly study and popularize best practices achieved in this area; establishing a strong bond between school, family, business and organizations. According to the analysis, the main goal of teachers should be the ability to observe and comprehensively analyze practical classes from the methodological, pedagogical and psychological points of view. As a result, teacher-engineers master the correct organization of each stage of education, the ability to choose the right methods in this process, timely understanding of scientific and methodological shortcomings and ways to eliminate them. When observing the lessons, it is necessary to carefully monitor each behavior, record achievements and shortcomings in a notebook in time, and at the end draw conclusions.

The organizational part is carried out as follows: - the state of the classroom, provision of equipment, start on time, attendance check, time spent on the organizational part, start and end; - checking homework and working on mistakes made during its implementation, asking questions about the topic covered (sequence, correctness of questions and answers by engineering teachers, logical connection of questions, accuracy and completeness of students' answers, their ability to use visual aids and tools, such as their activity[4]; - the implementation of preparing students for completing tasks, to what extent their identification is ensured, the process of studying a new complex topic, the time spent on this, the methods used, the level of technology use, what means are used, the implementation of the process of studying a new topic; - the degree of explanation of the topics of training by teachers-engineers in connection with previous topics,

the level of assimilation of new topics by students and the skill of teachers-engineers in its definition; - the content of educational topics meets the requirements of educational programs for newly acquired theoretical and practical knowledge, their compatibility with the textbook, the scientific nature of the studied materials, adequacy for the assimilation of new knowledge in the future, the relationship of theoretical and practical knowledge with previously studied materials; - the time spent on fixing new educational materials, the work of teacher-engineers in the process of fixing, the level of their effectiveness; - the activities of teacher-engineers, what kind of leadership they have, their exactingness in achieving the goal, the use of advanced pedagogical experience, the ability to manage a group, interact with students, set a pedagogical task, use modern technologies, use problem situations, involve students in activities; - compiling a summary based on an in-depth study of suitable topics in textbooks, special and methodical literature, selection of content, method, technology and means, didactic materials on problematic, production assignments for group classes; - conducting trainings and introspection in pedagogical activity, using its results to improve further educational work, conducting scientific and methodological work on this matter; - activity of students in the classroom, their propensity to learn, listening to teachers-engineers and acceptance of materials, discipline of students in this process, skill level; - announcing homework, providing the necessary instructions for its implementation, achieving the goal, the conclusions of teacher-engineers.

Thus, if a comprehensive assessment is given in the cases listed above during observation and analysis, then we can assume that the intended goal has been achieved. To do this, teachers-engineers require a creative approach to work. At the end of the lesson, students should be able to understand tasks, determine the information that is clearly visible in it, highlight the main words and phrases, highlight ideas that fully express their content, count these actions in the order they occur, explain the interconnectedness and generalizability of the presented ideas

and concepts.

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